

Research Article

Seroprevalence of Measles Virus Infection among 0-10 Years Old Children in Parts of North Western

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Abstract

Measles, one of the most infectious viral diseases of humans nearly all susceptible individuals in the absence of vaccination, is spread by the respiratory route and remains a major cause of mortality in children, particularly in developing countries. It is caused by measles virus (MV), which is an enveloped virus belonging to the genus morbillivirus of the family-paramyxoviridae. Measles is usually characterized by prodrome fever, maculopapular rash with one or a combination of coryza, cough, conjunctivitis and Koplik's spot. The study was conducted in some part of the North-West Nigeria with the aim to determine the seroprevalence of measles IgM and possible risk factors associated with the acquisition of the infection. A total of 725 children aged 0 to 10 years were selected for the study across the three states (Kano, Katsina and Zamfara). Measles-specific IgM antibodies were screened qualitatively using commercial ELISA IgM kit (Diagnostic Automation and Cortez, Calabasas, CA, USA). Measles IgM specific antibodies were detected in 334(44.4%) of the subjects. A higher prevalence of 53.2% was found in the age group 0-2years, and the least 21.4% in age group 8-10 years. There was a significant association between measles virus infection and age ($P=0.001$). Females show slightly higher prevalence 46.7% than males 42.1%, though there was no significant association ($P=0.03$). With respect to the parental occupation and education status, there was a significant association ($P> 0.05$) while vaccination status, number of vaccinations, travel history and contact history shows no significant statistical association ($P> 0.05$). However, in relation to previous measles history and crowded environment, statistically significant association was observed ($P< 0.05$). This is an indication that measles still persist in this part of the country despite the availability of safe and cost effective vaccine its persistence and burden is worrisome as observed in vaccinated and non- vaccinated children especially under five.

KEYWORDS: Measles, Prevalence, IgM, Antibody, North-West, ELISA

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Introduction

Measles is an acute highly contagious viral disease and a leading cause of vaccine preventable deaths among children, affecting mainly under-five children (Salako and Sholeye, 2015). Measles is caused by measles virus, an envelope, non-segmented virus with a single-stranded, negative-sense RNA genome, is a member of the genus Morbillivirus within the family Paramyxoviridae (Furuse *et al.*, 2010). Humans are the only natural hosts for measles virus, although other primates such as monkeys are also susceptible to measles and develop similar clinical diseases; these populations are not large enough to support sustained transmission (Griffin *et al.*, 2007).

Measles is characterized by fever, malaise cough, coryza, conjunctivitis and generalized maculo- papular rash with koplik spots appearing on the buccal mucosa 1-2 days before rash onset and may be noticeable for an additional 1-2days after rash onset (WHO, 2001). Infection confers lifelong immunity. Transmission occurs predominantly via respiratory route, by direct contact, breathing infected air or droplet emitted by coughing or sneezing and occasionally transmitted through the conjunctivae (Griffin *et al.*, 1990; Vries *et al.*, 2012). Although there is no treatment, most infected individuals recover by themselves except when complications result (Walter *et al.*, 2004).

Measles is a serious disease which usually affects susceptible children (WHO, 2009).It occurs throughout the world and remains a serious and common disease in developing countries (CDC, 2005). Studies have shown that among the burden of vaccine preventable diseases, measles is rank first with 38% disease burden (Onyiruika, 2011). Risk for illness and death from measles still exists in countries with variable routine vaccination coverage, as in Nigeria, where measles is a significant public health problem (CDC, 2009).

There have been fluctuations in the measles vaccine coverage in the country from 55% in 1981 through 59% in 1988, 26% in 1998 and 35% in 2003 (Abdulraheem *et al.*, 2011). In 2011 the national measles vaccination coverage is put at 62% with a very wide variation in the country that has once achieved coverage of 80% with routine immunization (Adeboye *et al.*, 2011). However,increased activities are being stepped up by various health regulatory agencies in a bid to control measles throughout the world, including Nigeria (Shena *et al.*, 2014).The present study was undertaken to determine the prevalence and ascertain the possible risk factors associated with acquisition of measles infection.

Materials and Method

Study location

The Northwestern region of Nigeria consists of Kano, Katsina, Zamfara, Sokoto, Kebbi, Jigawa and Kaduna States. Three states were selected for the purpose of this study which includes: Kano, Katsina and Zamfara States.

Study Design

The research was a descriptive cross sectional study, which covers both outbreak and sporadic cases within the study period in all the selected states. States were selected using simple random sampling. Using stratified sampling, each state was divided into three senatorial zones. Simple random sampling was used to select one local government from a zone, hospitals were randomly selected to represent a local government in each zone. In Kano State Hasiya Bayero Specialist Hospital (Kano municipal), General hospital Gwarzo, and General Hospital Wudil were selected. In Katsina State General Hospital Daura, General Hospital Funtua and Turai Yaradua hospital (Katsina municipal) were selected, while general hospital Anka, King Fahad women and children hospital and Kauran Namoda General Hospital were selected in Zamfara State.

Study population

Children 0-10 years of age with suspected measles case attending selected hospital in the study locations were included in the study. Ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical committee of the Ministries of Health of the states selected. Consent of parents and/or adult care givers of children under study were also obtained. Data were collected using a self-structured.

Sample Collection and Processing

A total of 752 samples was collected for the study across the nine selected Local Government Areas (LGAs) of the selected states, (Kano, Katsina and Zamfara). In Kano state 297 samples were collected while in Katsina and Zamfara States 231 and 224 were collected respectively. Three (3ml) of blood sample was collected from each patient and dispensed into sterile label plane containers. Serum sample was separated before being transported to the laboratory in a cold pack. The samples were stored at 4°C until assay time. All serological tests were carried out in the Department of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

Detection of Measles IgM Antibody

Using commercially available Enzyme immunosorbent assay (Measles IgM ELISA, Diagnostic Automation and Cortez, Calabasas, CA, USA), serum samples were assayed for specific IgM antibody against the measles virus. All assays were carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Data Analysis

Data were summarized as percentages, charts and frequency tables and results computed and analyzed using SPSS version 12. Chi-square test was performed, and statistical significance was established at a P value of ≤ 0.05 .

Results and Discussion

Out of seven hundred and fifty two (752) suspected measles cases screened for the presence of measles virus IgM, three hundred and thirty four (334) samples were positive, indicating an overall seroprevalence of 44.4% (Figure 1). The result of the present study contradicts those reported in Kaduna 32.2% and 21.1% (Chechet *et al.*, 2014; Olaitan *et al.*, 2015) respectively. It also contradicts those reported from other parts of the country with much lower prevalence of 8.0% by Adeboye *et al.* (2011) in Niger state and 16.5% by Chukuemeka *et al.*, (2013) in Abia State. Earlier study also reveals the prevalence of (15.6% and 32% in Lagos and Ilorin (Omilabu *et al.*, 1999; Babaniyi *et al.*, 1995) respectively. Our result however agrees with that of a study conducted by (WHO 2010) in some African countries with a prevalence of 41%. Higher prevalence recorded in this study might be as a result of our sampling criteria which include only suspected measles cases presented with febrile rashes. Higher prevalence were also reported by Adetunji *et al.* (2007) and Sheyin *et al.* (2016) 55% in Lagos and 54.1% in Kaduna State.

Figure 1: Seroprevalence of measles infection among children 0-10 years in some parts of North Western Nigeria.

The result of seroprevalence of measles IgM was analyzed according to some socio-demographic characteristics of the study subjects (Table 1). Measles IgM antibody was detected in all age groups, with a significantly higher seroprevalence 53.2% in age group 0-2 years and lower 21.4% in age group 8-10 years, showing significant association between measles virus infection and age ($\chi^2= 20.1$, $P =0.001$), although highest prevalence was observed in age group 0-2 years, the number of seropositive individual decreases with age. This agrees with studies conducted in Calabar, Lagos, Ibadan and Akwa Ibom (Etuk *et al.*, 2003; Adetunji *et al.*, 2007; Fetuga *et al.*, 2007 and Bassey *et al.*, 2010 respectively).

These early presentations of measles observed could be due to depletion of maternal antibody in the lower age group and/or variation in prevailing environmental factors as reported by Akramuzzaman *et al.* (2002). In addition, immunity acquired by older children over the years as a result of sub-clinical infections might provide the required protection against measles (Patel *et al.*, 2008). The age specific prevalence is inconsistent with the report from other parts of the world such as Saudi Arabia in which older children seem to be at risk of contacting the diseases with a peak age of 5-15 years as reported by Kamel, (1993).

Measles seroprevalence was also slightly higher in females 46.7% than males 42.1%, although the difference was not statistically significant. ($\chi^2= 1.619$, $P= 0.203$). This study compared favorably with (Gdalevich 2002; Bassey *et al.*, 2010 and Olaitan *et al.*, 2015). However, previous studies reported contrary in some parts of the country (Chukwu *et al.*, 2009; Chechet *et al.*, 2014 and Sheyin *et al.*, 2016). Higher prevalence in females observed in the present study might possibly be due to chance as the difference was not statistically significant. However (Aaby *et al.*, 1995), documented lower rates of immunization of females than males

There was a significant association between measles virus infection and parents occupation, with those from unemployed parents having the highest prevalence 57.1%, and the least prevalence of 37.6% among self-employed ($\chi^2=22.584$, $P =0.001$). The report of this study does not imply that measles infection occurs in a specific set of children regarding their parent's occupation as such could be due to chance rather than certainty.

Educational status of parents was found to be significantly associated ($\chi^2 =15.161$, $P =0.025$), with higher prevalence of 50.4% in parents with tertiary level of education and lower 34.2% in primary educated parents. Contrary to the result of our study is also a

report by Fowlkes *et al.*, (2011) and Mausez-Aumatel *et al.* (2015) who documented no association between measles prevalence and educational level of parents. This might be due to the endemic nature of measles virus infection in the study area so individuals have equal chances of acquiring measles infection.

Table 1: Seroprevalence of Measles IgM in relation to socio-demographic characteristics of 0-10 year's children in parts North Western Nigeria.

Socio-Demographic factors	No Examined	No positive (%)	Chi-square value	p-value
Age(years)				
0-2	357	190 (53.2)	20.1	0.001
2-4	252	100 (39.7)		
4-6	94	32 (34.0)		
6-8	35	9 (25.7)		
8-10	14	3 (21.4)		
Sex				
Male	373	157 (42.1)	1.619	0.203
Female	379	177 (46.7)		
Father's occupation				
Civil servant	152	63 (41.4)	23.871	0.001
Self employed	367	138 (37.6)		
Unemployed	233	133 (57.1)		
Education status of father				
Primary	117	40 (34.2)	9.348	0.025
Secondary	270	114 (42.2)		
Tertiary	230	116 (50.4)		
Informal	135	64 (47.4)		

P-value significant at ≤ 0.05 , OR = Odds Ratio

The seroprevalence of measles virus IgM with respect to vaccination status and previous infection is presented in Table 2. The association between the seroprevalence of measles virus IgM and vaccination status was not statistically significant ($\chi^2=2.555$, $P = 0.279$). Measles virus IgM was observed to be higher 42.1% in children who had been previously vaccinated against measles. This is, however, higher than 17.4%, 14.8% , 22.1% and 18.8% reported by (Adeboye *et al.*, 2010; Bassey *et al.*, 2010 Onyiruika, 2011

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and Duru *et al.*, 2014) respectively, though higher rates were reported from other Nigerian studies (Adetunji *et al.*, 2007 and Ahmed *et al.*, 2010).

Measles may occur at any age if there is no previous immunity. Therefore, the 46.3% of measles cases reported among unvaccinated children is not surprising. This is in conformity with the work of (Bassey *et al.*, 2010) who reported a seroprevalence of 47.4% among unvaccinated children. Higher measles seroprevalence was also documented in previous Nigerian studies among unvaccinated children (Fetuga *et al.*, 2007; Onyiruika *et al.*, 2011 and Duru *et al.*, 2014).

Children that received vaccination more than once had lower measles seroprevalence 33.3% compared to those that received vaccination once 47.1%. There was no association between MV infection and number of times of vaccination. ($\chi^2 = 0.160$, $P = 0.474$). Similar to this finding is the report of Linnemann *et al.*, (1982), who observed that 40% of children who received two doses of measles vaccine are less likely to have measles. This study pointed out that only subjects who had been vaccinated more than once had significantly lower chance of acquiring measles when compared to those vaccinated once as reported by (Shahrokh *et al.*, 2012).

The study established a significant association between MV seroprevalence and previous history of measles infection ($\chi^2 = 8.678$, $P = 0.013$). Children with a history of measles infection having a lower prevalence (33.8%) compared to children with no previous infection history (47.1%). These findings are comparable to a great extent with those of Kandpal *et al.*, (2003) which documented 5% seropositivity after measles infection due to the false history of measles and the possibility parent mistaken any other eruptive fever to be measles. An association between history of measles and presence of IgM was previously reported in Bolivian study (Cutts *et al.*, 1995).

Possible risk factors associated with measles virus infection were determined as presented in Table 3. The association between seroprevalence of measles IgM and travel history did not show statistical significance ($\chi^2=3.266$, $p=0.071$). This could be attributed to the endemic nature of the virus in our community and as such importation of measles cases are unlikely to occur.

Children who had no contact with infected persons recorded a slightly lower seroprevalence (44.0%), while (44.4%) seroprevalence was obtained among those who had contact with infected persons. There was no statistically significant difference between contact with infected individuals and measles seroprevalence ($\chi^2=0.030$, P

=0.862). This could be due to the nature of viral transmission, which apart from direct contact with infected person could be transmitted through droplet emission.

Table 2: Seroprevalence of Measles Virus IgM in relation to history of vaccination and measles infection

History of Vaccination/infection	No examined	No positive (%)	Chi-square value	p-value	OR
Vaccination					
Yes	294	124 (42.1)	2.555	0.279	
No	447	207 (46.3)			
Unknown	11	3 (27.3)			
Number of vaccinations					
Once	279	119 (42.7.6)	1.950	0.160	0.474
More than once	15	5 (33.3)			
History of Measles					
Yes	151	51 (33.8)	8.678	0.013	
No	597	281 (47.1)			
Unknown	4	2 (50.0)			

P-value significant at ≤ 0.05 , OR = Odds Ratio

Similarly, children who were exposed to the crowd had the higher seroprevalence of (46.5%) compared to those who were not (43.4%). The statistical association between the seroprevalence of measles virus and exposure to crowd was significant ($\chi^2=6.298$, $p=0.012$). Overcrowding has been documented by many researchers as a predisposing factor in the acquisition of the measles infection.

Table 3: Seroprevalence of Measles Virus IgM with respect to some risk factors of 0-10 year children with suspected measles

Risk factors	No examined	No positive (%)	OR	Chi-square value	p-value
Travel history					
Yes	42	13 (31.0)	0.543	3.266	0.071
No	710	321 (45.2)			
Contact history					
Yes	477	213 (44.7)	0.974	0.030	0.862
No	275	121 (44.0)			
Crowd					
Yes	624	290 (46.5)	0.603	6.298	0.012
No	128	44 (43.4)			

P-value significant at ≤ 0.05 , OR = Odds Ratio

Conclusion

This study reveals a seropositivity to measles IgM of 44.4% amongst 0-10 years in North West Nigeria. Factors found to be associated with measles in this study include age, parent's education status, occupation, overcrowding and previous exposure to measles. The results further reaffirm that measles remain endemic in our community, its persistence and burden is worrisome as observed in vaccinated and non- vaccinated children especially under five. There is urgent need for renewal of measles vaccination strategy and disease surveillance.

References

- Aaby, P. (1995). Assumptions and contradictions in measles and measles immunization research. Is measles good for something? *Social Science and Medicine*, 41:673-686.
- Abdulraheem, I.S., Onajole, A.T., Jimoh A.A. and Oladipo, A.R. (2011). Reasons for incomplete vaccination and factors for missed for missed opportunities among rural Nigerian children. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*, 3(4): 194-203.
- Adeboye, M., Omotayo A., Abdurashied A., Edith E., Usman A., Grace A., Abdullahi U., Solomon A., and Rotimi B. F. (2011). Measles in a Tertiary Institution in Bida, Niger State, Nigeria: Prevalence, Immunization Status and Mortality Pattern. *Oman Medical Journal*, 26(2): 114-117.
- Adetunji, O.O., Olusola E.P., Ferdinad F.F., Olorunyomi O.S., Idowu J.V., Ademola O.G. (2007). Measles among Hospitalized Nigerian Children. *The Internet Journal of Pediatrics and Neonatology*, 7(1):8-12
- Ahmed, P.A., Babaniyi I.B., Otuneye A. T., (2010). Review of childhood measles admission at the national hospital Abuja. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 13:413-416.
- Akramuzzaman, S.M., Cutts F.T., Hossain M.J., (2002). Measles vaccine effectiveness and risk factors for measles in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Bulletin of World Health Organization*, 80(10):776-782.
- Altınkaynak, E.V., Güraksın A., Kılıç A. and Yiğit N. (2005). The sero-epidemiology of measles in children from Eastern Turkey. *West Indian Medical Journal*, 54(4):doi.org/10.1590/S0043-31442005000400005

Babanniya, O. A., Parakoyi D. B., Aiyedun B. A., Bello M.A. (1995). Loss of maternally-acquired measles antibody during infancy in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Pediatrics*, 41(2):115-117.

Bassey, E.B., Moses A.E., Udo S.M., Umo A.N. (2010). The Impact of Immunization Control Activities on Measles Outbreaks in Akwa Ibom State, South-South, Nigeria. *Online Journal of Health and Allied Sciences*, 9(1):3.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2009). Global measles mortality, 2000–2008. *MMWR Morbidity Mortality Weekly Reports*, 58:1321-6.

Centers for Diseases Control and Prevention (CDC) (2005). Progress in reducing measles mortality worldwide, 1999-2003. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Reports*, 54:200-203.

Chechet, J., Ella E.E. and Ige, S., O. (2014). Seroprevalence of measles IgM in children 5-12 years from selected primary schools in Giwa Local Government Area, Zaria, Kaduna State. *Scientific Journal of Microbiology*, 3(2): 19-24.

Chukwu, O., Esiekpe M., Chukwuedo A. (2009). Detection of measles IgM antibodies in children at Kaduna state. *International Journal of Natural and Applied Science*, 5(1):<http://dx.doi.org/104314/ijonas.v5il.49945>.

Chukwuemeka, A.U. and Hycient P.A. (2013). The impact of declining vaccination coverage on measles control. A case study of Abia state Nigeria. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 15: 105.

Cutts, F.T., Bartoloni A., Guglielmetti P. (1995). Prevalence of measles antibody among children under 15 years of age in Santa Cruz, Bolivia: implications for vaccination strategies. *Trans Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 89:119–22.

Duru, C.O., Oliemen P. and Oyedeji O. A. (2014). A five year review of childhood measles at the Niger Delta university teaching hospital, Bayelsa state Nigeria. *Journal of Medicine and Medical sciences*, 5(4):78-86.

Etuk, I.S., Ekanem E.E., Udo J.J. (2003). Comparative analysis of measles morbidity and mortality in Calabar during the Expanded Programme on Immunization and the National Programme on Immunization Eras. *Nigerian Journal of Pediatrics*, 30(3): 81–85.

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Fetuga M.B., Njokanma O.F., Ogunfowora O.B., and Abiodun R. (2007). A ten - year study of measles admissions in a Nigerian teaching hospital. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 10:41-46.

Fikre E., Ayele W., Dejene, A., Messele, T., Abebe A., Cutts F.T. and Nokes D.J. (2003). Seroepidemiology of measles in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: implications for control through vaccination. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 130:507-519.

Fowlkes A., Witte D., Beeler J. and Audet S. (2011). Persistence of vaccine-induced measles antibody beyond age 12 months: a comparison of response to one and two doses of Edmonston-Zagreb measles vaccine among HIV-infected and uninfected children in Malawi. *Journal of Infectious Disease* 204: 149–157.

Furuse, Y., Suzuki, A. and Oshitani, H. (2010). Origin of measles virus: divergence from rinderpest virus between the 11th and 12th centuries. *Virology Journal*, 7:52.

Gdalevich, M. (2002). Measles antibody prevalence rates among young adults in Israel. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 30(3):165-9.

Griffin, D.E. (1990). Measles virus, In: Field B.N, Knipe D.M, Howley P.M, D. E. Griffin, R. A. Lamb, M. A. Martin, B. Roizman and S. E Strauss *Field virology*, New York: Williams and Wilkins. 1401-41.S12.

Griffin, D. E. (2007). Measles: In *Fields Virology*, 5th Edition. Knipe DM and Howley PM (Eds). Lippincott Williams and Wilkins Publishers. Pp. 1552-1585.

Kamel, M. I. (1993). Comparison of some epidemiological characteristics of vaccinated and unvaccinated measles cases in Saudi Arabia. *Alexandria Journal of Pediatrics* 3(4):545-552.

Kandpal, S.D., Negi, K.S., Khan, Z., Malik, A. (2003). Measles antibody status amongst five year unvaccinated children. *Indian Journal of Preventive Social Medicine* 34(S1-S2): 115-199.

Linnemann E., Smit, S. B., Beyene, B., Nigatu, W. and Babaniyi, O. A. (1982). Genetic characterization and progression of B3 measles genotype in Ethiopia: a study of five measles outbreak cases. *Ethiopian Medical Journal* 46: 79-85

Masuet-Aumatell, C, Ramon-Torrell J.M., Casanova-Rituerto A., Banqué Navarro M., DávalosGamboa M. R., Montaña Rodríguez S.L. (2013). Measles in Bolivia: a honeymoon period. *Vaccine* 31: 2097-2102.

Olaitan, A.E., Ella E.E., and Ameh J.B. (2015). Comparative seroprevalence of measles virus immunoglobulin M antibodies in children aged 0-8 months and a control population aged 9-23 months presenting with measles-like symptoms in selected hospitals in Kaduna state. *International Journal of General Medicine* 8:101-108.

Omilabu, S.A., Oyefolu A.O., Ojo O.O. and Audu R.A.(1999). Potency status and efficacy of the measles vaccine administered in Nigeria: A case study of three EPI centers in Lagos, Nigeria *African Journal of Medical Sciences*, 28:209-12.

Onyiriuka, A.N. (2011). Clinical profile of children presenting with measles in a Nigerian secondary health-care institution. *Journal of Infectious Disease and Immunology* 3:112.

Patel, P.K., Al-Awaidy S.T., Bawikar S., Al-Busaidy S. and Al-Mahrooqi S. (2008). Measles epidemiology and its implications for a vaccination Programme in Oman. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 14(3):5-8.

Salako, A.A and Sholeye O.O. (2015). Control of measles in Nigeria: A critical review of the literature. *British Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*5(2):160-168.

Shakrokh, I., Seyed-mohsen Z., and Majid Sartipi (2012). An investigation of measles outbreak in Southeast Iran. *Japan Journal of Infectious Disease*, 65: 45-51.

Shena, A.K., Fields, R. and McQuestionc, M. (2014). The future of routine immunization in the developing world: challenges and opportunities. *Global Health Science Practice*. 2(4): 381-394.

Sheyin, Z., Ede F.R., Essien U.C., Shindang, J., Bigwan E.I. (2016). Detection of Measles Virus IgM Antibodies among Individuals Suspected of Measles in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 6(1): 87-91.

Vries, R.D., Mesmam, A.W., Geijtenbeek, T.B., Duprex, W.P., and Swart, R.L. (2012). Pathogenesis of Measles. *Current Opinion in Virology*. 2 (3): 248-255.

Walter, A.O., Robert, T.P., and Neal, A.H. (2004). The clinical Significant of Measles. *Journal of Infectious Disease*, 189(1): S4- S16.

W.H.O (2001). Expanded program on immunization. Nomenclature for describing the genetic characterization of wild-type measles virus (update) part 1. *Weekly Epidemiological Records*, 32: 247-252.

W.H.O (2009). Measles vaccines: W.H.O Position Paper. *Weekly Epidemiology Records*, 35(84): 349-360.

W.H.O (2010). WHO/UNICEF Joint Statement: Global plan for reducing measles mortality. *Weekly Epidemiology Records*, 9(87):73-80.